

CODE SCORES IN LIVE CODING PRACTICE

Thor Magnusson

Department of Music

University of Sussex

Brighton, BN1 9RH, UK

t.magnusson@sussex.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

This paper explores live coding environments in the context of notational systems. The improvisational practice of live coding as combining both composition and performance is introduced and selected systems are discussed. The author's Threnoscope system is described, but this is a system that enables the performer to work with both descriptive and prescriptive scores that can be run and altered in an improvisational performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The live coder sits on stage and writes software in front of a live audience. The desktop is projected on the wall in a gesture of sharing and audience engagement [1, 2]. In the past decade, live coding has become a popular performance practice, supported by the diverse interpreted and high level programming languages that suit the practice. Furthermore, the popular hacker and maker cultures are affecting general culture such that coding is now considered a creative activity on par with drawing or playing an instrument. The live coding community has played an important role here and been active in disseminating the practice by sharing code, organizing festivals and conferences, and establishing research networks.

Code is a form of notation that works extremely well in musical composition, especially when the aim is to write non-linear, interactive, or context aware music [3]. Although general-purpose languages can be used for musical live coding, many live coders have created their own mini-languages for a particular performance style, genre, or even a performance. The new language becomes an instrument, a framework for thinking, with strong considerations of notational design. Here, language designers have invented graphical interfaces like we find in Pure Data or Max/MSP; game interfaces, as in Dave Griffiths' *Al Jazaari*; functional notation, like McLean's *Tidal*; or Chris Kiefer's physical controllers that encode genetic algorithms of sound synthesis [4].

2. NOTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Notation is a way of communicating abstract ideas to an interpreter, and in live coding that interpreter is typically a compiler called the "language interpreter." Standard Music Notation is a system of notation that has developed

from the general recognition that symbols can capture more information, coherent in meaning between composers, interpreters and cultures, in a smaller space than natural language or bespoke new symbolic languages. Standard Music Notation is a cognitive tool that has developed with requirements for a standard language and concerns about sight-reading and rapid understanding. Composers are able to rely on the performer's expertise and creative interpretation skills when the piece is played. Conversely, in the symbolic notation for computer music composition and performance, we encounter an important difference in the human and the computer capacity for interpretation: the human can tolerate mistakes and ambiguity in the notation, whereas the computer cannot. Natural language programming of computers is clearly possible, for example:

```
produce a sine wave in A
name this synth "foo"
wrap this in an ADSR envelope
repeat foo four times per second
name this pattern "ping"
```

However, the problem here is one of syntax: what if the coder writes "Sine" instead of "sine," "440" instead of "A," or "every 0.25 second" instead of "four times per second?" The cognitive load of having to write natural language with the programming language's unforgiving requirements for perfect syntax makes the natural language approach less appealing than writing in traditional programming languages, for example in functional or object orientated languages. Of course, semi-natural language programming languages have been invented, such as COBOL, Apple Script, or Lingo. The problems with those were often that they became quite verbose and the 'naturalness' of their syntax was never so clear. Consequently, in a more familiar object oriented dot-syntax, the above might look like:

```
w = Sine("foo", [freq, 440]);
w.addEnvelope(\adsr);
p = Pattern("ping");
p.seq(\foo, 0.25);
```

In both cases we have created a synthesizer and a pattern generator that plays the synth. The latter notation is less prone to mistakes, and for the trained eye the syntax actually becomes symbolic through the use of dots, camelCase, equals signs, syntax coloring, and brackets with arguments that are differently formatted according to type. This is called 'secondary notation' in computer science parlance, and addresses the cognitive scaffolding offered by techniques like colorization or indentation [5].

possibility of storing the state of the code at any given time in the performance. This is done by writing a snapshot with a name: the snapshot can then be recalled at any time, where running new code is subsequently muted (and changes color), and agents whose score has changed return to their state when the snapshot was taken.

A recent live coding environment by Charlie Roberts called *Gibber* [11] takes this secondary notation and visual representation of music further than *ixi lang*: here we can see elements in the code highlighted when they are played: the text flashes, colors change, and font sizes can be changed according to what is happening in the music. *Gibber* allows for any textual element to be mapped to any element in the music. The code becomes a visualization of its own functionality: equally a prescription and description of the musical processes.

```

a = Drums( 'x*ox*xo' )
b = Drums( 'x*xo-x*o' )
c = Drums( 'ox*xo-x*x*' )
Master.fadeOut(32)

c.text.fontSize = c.Out
c.text.fontSize.max = 20

Master.fx.add( Crush( 'clean' ) )
Master.fx[0].sampleRate = Line(1,.1,measures(64) )
Master.fx[0].bitDepth = Line(16,2.5,measures(64) )

c.pitch.seq( [.5,1,-1,2,0,-4].rnd() )

a.note.values.stepSize.seq( [-1,1,-2,2], 1.25 )
b.note.values.rotate.seq( 1,1 )
c.note.values.rotate.seq( -1,1 )

```

Figure 4. *Gibber*. Here textual code can change size, color or font responding to the music. All user-defined.

Gibber is created in the recent Web Audio API, which is a JavaScript system for browser-based musical composition. As such it offers diverse ways of sharing code, collaborating over networks in real-time or not.

All of the systems above use visual elements as both primary and secondary notation for musical control. The notation is prescriptive – aimed at instructing computers – although elements of secondary notation can represent information that could be said to be of a descriptive purpose [12]. The four systems have in common the constrained set of functions aimed to explore particular musical ideas. None of them – bar *Gibber* perhaps – are aimed at being general audio programming systems, as the goals are concerned with live coding: real-time composition, quick expression, and audience understanding.

4. THE THRENOSCOPE

In the recent development of the *Threnoscope* system, the author has explored representational notation of live coding. This pertains to the visualization of sound where audible musical parameters are represented graphically. The system is designed to explore microtonality, tunings, and scales; and in particular how those can be represented in visual scores aimed at projection for the audience.

The *Threnoscope* departs from linear, pattern-based thinking in music and tries to engender the conditions of musical stasis through a representation of sound in a circular interface where space (both physical space and

pitch space) is emphasized, possibly becoming more important than concerns of time.

The system is object oriented where the sound object – the ‘drone’ – gets a graphical representation of its state. This continuous sound can be interacted with through code, the graphical user interface, MIDI controllers, and OSC commands, and changes visually depending upon which parameters are being controlled. The user can also create ‘machines’ that improvise over a period of time on specific sets of notes, as defined by the performer. These machines can be live coded, such that their behavior changes during their execution. Unlike the code score, discussed below, the machines are algorithmic: they are not intended to be fully defined, but rather to serve as an unpredictable accompaniment to the live coder.

Figure 5. The *Threnoscope* in 8-channel resolution. The straight crossing lines are speakers. The circles are harmonics, and the colored wedges are (moving) drones.

Figure 5 shows the circular interface where the innermost circle is the fundamental frequency, with the harmonics repeated outwardly. The lines crossing the interface represent the audio channels or speakers (the system can be set from 2 to 8 channels). The sound/drone can have a length extending up to 360 degrees, but it can also be short and move fast around the space. Figure 6 depicts the system with the command line prompt on the right, and a console underneath that reports on the state of the engine, errors in code, or events being played in a running score. By clicking on a particular drone, its sonic information appears in the console in a format that gives the coder quick entry to manipulate the parameters.

Musical events in the *Threnoscope* system are created through code instructions. Since the default envelope of the drone is an ASR (Attack, Sustain, Release) envelope, a note duration can range from a few milliseconds to an infinite length. Each of the speaker lines could be seen as a static playhead, where notes either cross it during their movement or linger above it with continuous sound. A

The first method simply plays the score without a graphical representation. This is very flexible, as multiple scores can be played simultaneously, or the same score started at different points in time. Scores can be stopped at will. Whilst the scores are typically played without any visual representation, it can be useful to observe the score graphically. The second method creates the above-mentioned graphical representation of the score shown in Figure 7. For a live performance, this can be helpful as it allows the performer to interact with the score during execution. The visual representation of the score can also assist in gaining an overview of a complex piece.

For this author, the code score has been a fruitful and interesting feature of the system. Using scores for digital systems aimed at improvisation becomes equivalent to how instrumentalists incorporate patterns into their motor memory. The use of code scores question the much broken unwritten ‘rule’ that a live coding performance should be coded from scratch. It enables the live coder work at a higher level, to listen more attentively to the music (which, in this author’s experience, can be difficult when writing a complex algorithm), and generally focus more on the compositional aspects of the performance.

7. CONCLUSION

This short paper has discussed domain specific programming languages as notational systems. Live coding systems are defined as often being idiosyncratic and bespoke to their authors’ thought processes. The Threnoscope and its code score was presented as a solution to certain problems of performance and composition in live coding, namely of delegating activities to actors such as machines or code scores.

8. REFERENCES

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